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Education Beyond Intelligence: Restoring the Heart of Humanity

We have read and learned from the book of Genesis in the Bible that God created everything in this world, including man. God created man in his own likeness and image. He mandated man to be the steward of His creations. Man lives in harmony and prosperity until he and his wife disobey God. As a consequence, they were expelled from the prosperous garden of Eden, and they had to work hard to survive.

As time passes, the human population increases massively. Through the continuous efforts of man to develop innovations and contribute something to the human race, we can say we are in the modern information era. Nowadays, information is so digital that we can know anything that triggers our curiosity by simply surfing the net. Hence, we can easily learn, relearn, or unlearn anything, anytime, and anywhere. However, are we really that intuitive enough? Can we really call ourselves educated? With the advent of modern technology, we can also witness some horrible acts of man that we might be afraid to say how evil a man can be. There might be good people who really try to be moral and humane, but there are also people who do the opposite. It is sad to hear the terrible news of a teenage boy who brutally shot children and teachers inside an elementary school. Some children kill their parents, and parents who hurts his/her family. Now, are we really that educated? Or are we really doing our job to be a great steward of God's creation?

Many people still lost themselves in the dark and choose to stay there. Some people do not know the reason for their existence and the purpose of their lives. On the other hand, we all have stories to tell. These people who do evil may have good reasons. I mean, there is no excuse for doing bad, especially if it has the two elements of moral responsibility, such as knowledge and free will. The bottom line is that some people might also be victims of their own nightmares and horrible experiences that shape the kind of person they are. I strongly believe in the purity of man's heart, that there is always good in each man's heart, even if he is the most wicked person who has ever lived in this world. Maybe we need to be more understanding and kinder. Each person has their own loads, but if we choose to help, maybe we can make a difference. Sometimes these people need that support system to rebuild themselves. This is the reason why I chose to be a teacher. This is my forever passion, mission, vocation, vision, and profession. In this way, I can help thousands or even a million young adults and future professionals to be on the right track. With all the teaching strategies and pedagogy, I will help them find the meaning of their existence and the purpose of their precious lives. At the end of the day, I will ASPIRE to INSPIRE, until I EXPIRE.